

THE SYNTACTICAL FEATURES OF FORMAL WORK STYLE IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

Linguistics

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Abstract

The researches which are carried out in the field of formal work style, is given attention in this article, it is said about inner separation of formal style, such as the style of the law language, the style of diplomatic correspondence, the style of work documents, and the different aspects in the syntactic features of these species. In addition, the syntactic features of the style of work documents are described in detail, using type of simple sentences in this style according to the expression purpose, using type of head parts according to the participation, using complicated simple sentences, and using types of composite sentence are given on the basis of samples. Using parts and types of speech with which requirement in text types are based and are given reasons on the basis of examples which are given from document types. Together with giving information about the types of sentences which are used in the text of the work documents in the article, it is also said that what types of sentences are used in which type of the document. The formed phrases of documents belong to work documents have been shown, participation of syntactic units have been noted in making these phrases.

The formal work style in the Uzbek linguistics is partly studied (3, 4, 5). The formal work style and its features were mentioned in these researches, and the appearance and the history of formation of the formal style was highlighted in the monographic plan by K.Omonov (8). Also, A.Mamajonov also wrote about the stylistics of formal style, mainly, about subordinate clauses in his doctoral thesis dedicated to “The stylistic features of the subordinate clauses of the Uzbek language” (6). The authors of the practical guidance in the theme “The office work in the Uzbek language” and “The office work” have also mentioned to the style of formal work style (1, 2). Based on these resources, we have talked about syntactic features of documents of office work.

The main task of the formal style is to express the formal relationships. Its basis consists of the office work. In turn, this bases the division of the formal work style into directions such as the language of laws, the language of diplomatic correspondence, and the language of the work documents. All three directions of the formal work style differ from each other with some aspects. The language of laws and diplomatic correspondence style has studied in the Uzbek linguistics (4,5,7). However, these three directions of the formal style are not studied with comparison to each other. The syntactic feature of the style of office work is unique. Namely, above mentioned two styles: the style of the language of laws differs from the style of the diplomatic correspondence.

If the style of the language of the law only consists of declarative sentences, it differs that the imperative sentences are not used, declarative sentences and imperative sentences are used in the style of diplomatic and commercial correspondence, sharply differ from the style of work documents according to the form and expression.

The sentences are written with the enthusiastic spirit in the style of diplomatic and commercial correspondence: “*Shuni ma'lum qilish sharafiga muyassar bo'ladiki ...*” (“*It is the honor to declare that ...*”). The imperative sentences in this style does not express pure command meaning, it expresses more the request meaning: :“ *Sizga bo'lgan yuksak hurmatimga ishonch bildirgaysiz*” (“*Trust in my high esteem for you*”). Sentences which often expressed the request meaning are expressed in the form of declarative sentences, namely, the sentence ends with “*I hope, I trust*”, not with “*I ask*”: “*Fursatdan foydalanib yana bir bor ...ga umid bildiradi (ishonch bildiraman)*” (“*I hope (trust) again once again ...*”).

Declarative sentences and imperative sentences are used in the style of work documents.

Declarative sentences more expresses to inform: *Abdulla Rahmatillayevich Umarov Farg'ona poyabzal korxonasida sozlovchi bo'lib ishlaydi.(ma'lumotnomadan); Arizamga o'rta ma'lumot va maxsus ish yurituvchilik kursini tugatganlik to'g'risidagi guvohnomamni ilova qilaman.(arizadan); Men,... ushbu vasiyatnoma orqali quyidagi topshiriqni beraman. (vasiyatnoma). (Abdulla Rahmatillayevich Umarov works as an adjuster in the Fergana shoe factory (from the reference); I attach the certificate about my secondary education and completion of a special office work course. (from the application); I,... will give you the following task through this will. (wills)).*

Imperative sentences serve to do the following tasks in the style of work documents:

a) it uses to express the formal order: *Devonxona mudirasi Z.I.Alieva mehnat shartnomasidagi muddat tugashi munosabati bilan O'zR MK... moddasi,... bandiga ko'ra 2000.20.05.dan o'z lavozimidan Bo'shatilsin. (Dismiss the head of the law-court Z.I.Alieva from her position according to the section...., article... of the Work codex of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 2000.20.05 because of ending the date in the employment contract. (command). In this case, words representing the command are written with the capital letters: *Oylik maoshi... so'm miqdorida Belgilansin.; Buyruqni nazorat qilish direktor o'rinbosari Z.Valiev zimmasiga Yuklatilsin; (Be appointed the salary in the amount... soums; “Lay upon to control the command to the deputy director Z.Valiev;).**

b) It expresses the request meaning: *Meni fakultetga kotiba vazifasiga ishga qabul qilishingizni so'rayman. (arizadan); Mazkur masalani institut bilan kelishgan holda ijobiy hal qilishingizni so'rayman. (bildirishnoma) (I ask you to accept me to the job as a secretary in the faculty. (from the application); I ask you to resolve this issue in a positive way agreeing with the Institute. (memorandum)).*

v) It expresses the command and will: *Men vafotim oldidan ...ga vasiyat qilib goldiraman. (I leave by testament to ... before my death).*

In this style, simple extended sentences are not practically used. The ordinary sentences are usually made in the form of simple extended sentences: *Iqtisod bo'limining katta mutaxassisi*

A.Sadirbekova 2000.22.05.dan o`z roziligi bilan shu bo`limning yetakchi mutaxassisi lavozimiga O`tkazilsin. (A senior specialist of the Economics department, A.Sadirbekova, is appointed with her consent to the position the leading expert of this department from 2000.22.05).

The one-part sentence and two-part sentence types of the ordinary sentences are actively used. For example, *Nozima Karimova Olimova 1999.20.05.dan 15000 so`mlik maosh bilan bo`yash sexining katta muhandisi lavozimiga Tayinlansin.(...), Buyruq bilan tanishdim. (Be appointed Nozima Karimova Olimova as a senior engineer of the painting shop with a salary of 15,000 sum from 1999.20.05 (...), Familiarized with the command).*

Sometimes the use of this type of sentences will depend on how the document will be formed. In particular, if the text of the application is formed with the simple way and the issue which is observed in it, is not complicated (it does not require the explanation), then one-part sentence is used: *Meni institutning katta o`qituvchisi lavozimidan o`z ixtiyoriga ko`ra ozod etishingizni so`rayman. (I ask you to dismiss me from the position of the senior teacher of the institute according to my consent).* As you can see, the text of the documents consists of one-part sentence. Contrarily, if the issue which is observed in application requires explanation, its text consists of a few sentences and two-part sentences are used: *Mening erim va bolalarimning otasi Turdi Sodiqovich Bozorov 1998 yil 23 may kuni vafot etdi. Biz mazkur adresdagi merosiy xonadonda yashab kelmoqdamiz. (My husband and my children's father, Turdi Sodikovich Bozorov, was died on May 23, in 1998. We have lived in the house aforementioned address which we inherited from husband.)*

The definitely personal sentence type of one-part sentences is actively used. We can give sentences which are formed *сұрайман* (I ask) in the application. It is not used in the text of the application because there is the name of the person who filed the application in the address part of this type of documents. The word *men* (I) is not used in the text because the person is mentioned above, and it is often stated in the definitely-personal sentences form: ... *ni so`rayman; buyruq bilan tanishdim; omonat kassadagi 1320-raqam bo`yicha saqlanayotgan pul jamg`armasini Karim Hamidovich Botirovga vasiyat qilib qoldiraman; ...ni ...ga muvofiq qabul qilaman. (I ask...; I familiarize with the command; I bequeath my money savings deposit on the security deposit number 1320 to Karim Khamidovich Batirov; I agree with...).*

Generalized-personal sentences and impersonal sentences are not used in the style of work documents.

Impersonal sentences are used in the following cases:

1. When a general rule is stated for employees of institution, company, or organization: *Yo`l qog`ozini bir yuk avtomobilidan ikkinchisiga berish ruxsat etilmaydi. (yo`riqnoma). (It is not permitted to give the road document from one lorry to another. (instruction)).*

2. When the person is not indicated, because the person is clear who are given the command or decree: *Oylik maoshi ... so`m miqdorida Belgilansin. (buyruq). May oyida ikki xodimni Berlinga xizmat safariga jo`natish uchun aniq tavsiya berilsin. (ko`rsatma) (Be appointed the salary in the amount ... soums (command); Give clear recommendation to two workers to send to Berlin in May (instruction).* In this case, the verb is in passive voice. The additional of passive voice provides the formality, not the uncertainty.

Sometimes the additional command is given as the instruction to the executor:

1. *3-sexda zudlik bilan ta'mirlash ishlari o`tkazilsin. (Farmoyish) (Repair immediately at 3rd the workshop. (decree)).*

2. *Ta'mirlash ishlarini nazorat qilish 3-sex boshlig`i S.Turopovga topshirilsin. (Controlling over the repair works should be given to the head of the 3rd workshop S.Turopov.*

3. When the person who is performing the action, is known in the text of the document: *Ushbu vasiyatnoma 2 nusxada tuzildi va imzolandi. (This will is made in two copies and signed).*

As above mentioned, the two-part sentences are used in extended way. We can see the participle and gerund device of simple extended sentences in this style: - *"U merosdan voz kechib, 1997 yil 20 martda mening foydamga merosdan voz kechganligi haqida Toshkent shahar 15-davlat notarial idorasiga ariza bergan."* (arizadan); *Bizning nomimizdan hovli-joy oldi-sotdisi bo`yicha tuzilgan va Toshkent shahar 1-davlat notarial idorasi tomonidan 1995 yil 8 noyabrda 3-1310- raqami bilan ro`yxatga olinib tasdiqlangan shartnomani bekor qilishingizni so`raymiz.(ariza); Men, Enaxon Saidqulova, erim Ibrohim Soliyevich Saidqulovning birgalikdagi nikohimiz davrida sotib olingan, Toshkent viloyati Qibray tumani Do`rmon qishlog`i Xislat ko`chadagi 21-raqamli hovli-joyni hadya qilishiga rozilik bildiraman.(arizadan) ("He denied the inheritance and applied to the 15th state notary's office in Tashkent on March 20, 1997 that he denied the inheritance for my profit.", We kindly ask you to cancel the signed contract which were formed on our behalf by purchase and sale of house registered with number 3-1310 by the 1st Notary's Office of Tashkent city on 8 November in 1995. (application); I, Enaxon Saidkulova, would agree that my husband, Ibrohim Solievich Saidkulov, has donated the number 21st apartment which we bought during our mutual marriage, on Xislat Street in Durmon village, Kibray district of Tashkent region. (From application) (one-part sentences)).*

The simple parts of speech are in homogeneous form: *Tuzatilgan yoki yozuvlari o`chirilgan yo`l qog`ozlari tasdiqlovchi hujjat sifatida qabul qilinmaydi; (Yo`riqnoma); ...sotishi, topshirishi, ayirboshlashi, ijaraga berishi, vaqtinchalik foydalanish uchun bepul yoki qarzga berishi mumkin. (nizom). (Corrected or dismissed road documents will not be accepted as confirming documents; (Instruction); ... may give free or debt in order to sell, transfer, exchange, lease, or use temporarily. (charter)).*

It is strongly required that the parts of speech should be in the usual order. Documents are written on behalf of I or III person. Documents, such as instruction, charter, indication, protocol, reference are written on the behalf of III person, announcement, wills, bibliographies, recommendation, receipt, explanatory notes, application, reports, are written on behalf of I person. Some documents can be written in both forms: order, contract, employment agreement, act, warrant.

Also, each document has peculiar forms of formed sentence by syntactical aspect. The sentences such as “...so`m maosh bilan...lavozimiga tayinlansin”; “...o`z xohishiga ko`ra...lavozimidan ozod qilinsin”; “...boshqa ishga o`rganligi munosabati bilan...lavozimidan ozod qilinsin.”; “Oylik maoshi shtat jadvali bo`yicha...so`m miqdorida Belgilansin”; “...davrida...vazifasi...ga Yuklatilsin.” (Be appointed to position with... sum wage”; “Dismiss.... with his/ her consent from position”; “Dismiss ... from position because of transfer to another job”; “Be appointed wage in the amount of ... with manning table”; “Lay upon in ... period”; are used in the text of command, the sentences such as “Meni...vazifasiga ishga qabul qilishingizni so`rayman”; “Meni...lavozimiga ishga qabul qilishingizni so`rayman”; “Meni...lavozimidan o`z ixtiyorimga ko`ra ozod etishingizni so`rayman”; “...ga ruxsat berishingizni so`rayman” (“I ask you to accept me to work to the ...position”; “I ask you to accept to the position”; “I ask you to dismiss me from the position with my consent”; “I ask you to permit”) are used in the text of the application, the sentences such as “Men,..., ...ga...uchun ishonch bildiraman”; “...ga ...bajarishga vakolat beradi” (“I believe to ...for ...”; “Authorize ... to ...”) are used in the text of warrant, the sentences such as ..da...bo`lib ishlaydi; “O`rtacha oylik maoshi ...so`m”, “Ma`lumotnoma ...ga taqdim etish uchun berildi.” (“He/She works as in ...”; “His/Her average wage is sum”; “Reference is given for giving to ...”) are used in the text of reference, the sentences such as “.. tufayli ...ga qatnasha olmadim”, “... sababli ...ni bajara olmadim”, “... uchun ...ga kechikib keldim” (“I could not attend to ... because of ..”, “I could not do it ... because of...”, “I’m late for ... for ...”) are used in the text of the explanatory notes. In addition, the phrases such as “ilova qilamiz”, “qayta yo`llaymiz” (“We attach”, “We resend”) are specific to the attachment letter, the phrase “...ни сўраймиз” (“We ask ...”) is specific to request letter and the phrases “... tasdiqlaymiz”, “ma`lum qilamiz” (“We confirm ...”, “We inform ...”) are specific to confirmation letter. These forms, which are specific to texts of document, make easy to office work. They will greatly simplify the work of the person who write the document and receive the document. “The documentary writers say that “the documents are not written, but they are formed” according to the participation of these formed combinations (2, p. 17)”.

Insertions are used: *Iqtisod bo`limining katta mutaxassisi A.Sadirbekova 2000.22.05.dan, o`z roziligi bilan, shu bo`limning yetakchi mutaxassisi lavozimiga O`tkazilsin. (The senior specialist of the Economics department A. Sadirbekova is appointed as the leading specialist of this department from 2000.22.05, with her consent).*

Sometimes the sentences which insertions are used, in the text will be formed, so that they can be used in the following ways without any limitation: *Navoiy nomidagi Til va adabiyot instituti ma'muriyati nomidan direktor T.Mirzaev (keyingi o`rinlarda "Direktor" deb yuritiladi) bir tomon,... (keyingi o`rinlarda "Xodim" deb yuritiladi) ikkinchi tomon bo`lib ushbu shartnomani quyidagilar haqida tuzdilar. ("On behalf of the Institute of Language and Literature named after Navoi, the director T.Mirzaev (hereinafter referred to as the "Director") from one hand,... (hereinafter referred to as "worker") from the second hand, sign the contract about the followings.*

Hereinafter, we may refer the followings as the formed phrase:.... (hereinafter referred to as "...")... *from one hand,...(hereinafter referred to as "...") from the second hand, sign the contract about the followings.* It is seen, that only necessary words must be put their own place. These formed phrase, used in formal style, make it much easier to work.

Although the direct speech is not used in the style of work documents, the indirect speech is commonly used: *"bir oydan keyin o`g`limni olgani keldim, lekin javobgar uni menga berishdan bosh tortib, uni mendan ko`ra yaxshiroq tarbiyalay olishini aytdi" (da'vo arizasidan), "Bizning bir qancha eslatishlarimizdan keyingina tayyorlov idorasi shu yilning 12 avgustida, omborxonalarining tirbandligi sababli, qolgan 45 tonna olmani qabul qila olmasligini, shuning uchun jamoa xo`jaligi ana shu olmalarni o`zi xohlaganday tasarruf etishi mumkinligini ma'lum qildi. " (da'vo arizasi), "Shartnomaning ijro muddati tilxat bo`yicha 1998 yil 1 yanvarda tugagan bo`lishiga qaramay, javobgar, mening ana shu pulsiz ham yashay olishim mumkinligini aytib,qarzni qaytarishdan bosh tortmoqda", "Men bilan shartnoma tuzar ekan, javobgar shu yil davomida davlat kvartirasi olishi kerakligini, shunday bo`lgan taqdirda, menga qarashli xonani belgilangan muddatdan oldinroq bo`shatib berishini ta'kidlagan edi" ("After one month I came to pick up my son, but the defendant refused to give him to me and said that he would train better my son than me" (from the claimant's application); "After our some mentions, the procurement department announced on August 12 of this year that it could not accept the remaining 45 tonnes apples due to the warehouses were full, so the community farm could possess those apples as it wanted". (the claimant's application); "Although the execution period of the contract ended on January 1, 1998 by voucher, the responsible person refuses to repay the debt, saying that I can live without this money", "When I sign a contract with the defendant, the defendant emphasizes that he must receive a state flat for that year, and, if so, would release a room whing belongs to me, before the deadline").*

Before speaking about composite sentences which come in the text of the documents, we should emphasize that sentences with participle and gerund which are like to the subordinate clauses by form, are commonly used in the texts. The followings are the proof of this: sentence with participle – *Bizning nomimizdan hovli-joy oldi-sotdisi bo`yicha tuzilgan va Toshkent shahar 1-davlat notarial idorasi tomonidan 1995 yil 8 noyabrda 3-1310- raqami bilan ro`yxatga olinib tasdiqlangan shartnomani bekor qilishingizni so`raymiz.(ariza); Men, Enaxon Saidqulova, erim Ibrohim Soliyevich Saidqulovning birgalikdagi nikohimiz davrida sotib olingan, Toshkent viloyati Qibray tumani Do`rmon qishlog`i Xislat ko`chasidagi 21-raqamli hovli-joyini hadya qilishiga*

rozilik bildiraman.(arizadan) (We kindly ask you to cancel the signed contract which were formed on our behalf by purchase and sale of house registered with number 3-1310 by the 1st Notary's Office of Tashkent city on November 8 in 1995. (application); I, Enaxon Saidkulova, would agree that my husband, Ibrohim Solievich Saidkulov, has donated the number 21st apartment which we bought during our mutual marriage, on Xislat Street in Durmon village, Kibray district of Tashkent region. (From application) and sentences with gerund - "U merosdan voz kechib, 1997 yil 20 martda mening foydamga merosdan voz kechganligi haqida Toshkent shahar 15-davlat notarial idorasiga ariza bergan.", "Men 2000 yil 14 avgust kuni 11-yo`nalishda qatnaydigan trolleybusda ketayotib, Akmal Ikromov tuman ichki ishlar bo`limi tomonidan 1995 yilda berilgan pasportimni yo`qotdim." ("He denied the inheritance and applied to the 15th state notary's office in Tashkent on March 20, 1997 that he denied the inheritance for my profit.", "On August 14, 2000, when I was going on a 11th departure trolley bus, I lost my passport issued by the Akmal Ikromov District Department of Internal Affairs in 1995.).

We can see all types of subordinate clauses in the text of documents. In particular,

a) compound sentences: *Ayni vaqtda idishda qolgan yonilg`i miqdori o`lchanadi va bu o`lchov yo`l qog`ozining tegishli joyiga yozib qo`yiladi.(yo`riqnoma) (At the same time, the amount of fuel remaining in the container is measured and this measurement is written to the appropriate place on the road document. (instruction))*

It has been known from our observation that the compound sentences type which is linked with the copulative conjunction and disjunctive conjunction, is used: *Bizning kelishuvimiz paytida Usmon To`raevich Ahatov bor edi va u shartnoma tuzish holatini tasdiqlashi mumkin; Bu yerda doimiy yashash uchun xotinim va bolalarim ham kelishgan, biroq o`z yashash joyimiz yo`q; 1997 yil iyulida javobgar o`z oilasini tashlab, boshqa ayol bilan yashamoqda, lekin qizini boqish uchun moddiy yordam ko`rsatmayapti; (During our agreement, Usmon Turaevich Ahatov was here and he could confirm the contractual status; My wife and children come here to live permanently but we do not have a place to live for us; In July 1997 the responsible person left his family and lives with another woman, but he does not provide financial support for his daughter;)*

b) The subordinate clauses without conjunction: *Har bir avtomobil bo`yicha yuk avtomashinalari ishlarining ko`rsatkichi kunma-kun tartibda yuk avtomobillari ishlarining hisob-kitobi qaydnomasida yozib boriladi, shu asosda dispetcher har bir oy uchun avtomobillar ishlari hisob-kitobining qo`shma qaydnomasini tuzadi; Nashriyotga biriktirilgan asosiy va aylanma mablag`lar uning Nizom jamg`armasini tashkil etadi,uning miqdori nashriyot balansi bilan belgilanadi; (Indicator of truck's work by each car is recorded on a daily basis in the calculation of the truck's work, so the dispatcher compiles a joint notation account of cars' work for each month in this order; The main and circulating assets attached to the publishing house constitute its Charter Fund, its amount is determined by the balance of publishing house;)*

v) subordinate subordinate clauses are commonly used in this style. Here we give sentences belong to its some types.

Time clauses – *Ish kuni tugagandan so`ng, yo`l qog`ozi dispetcherga qaytarilishi kerak; Shartnoma muddati tugagandan so`ng, M.T.Olimov turar joyni tegishli tartibda va yashashga yaroqli holda topshirish majburiyatini oladi. (After ending of the working day, the road documents should be returned to the dispatcher; After ending the expiration of the contract, M.T.Olimov has obligation to return accommodation in a proper and viable manner for living).*

Causal clause: *Ota-onam bilan birga Chinoz tumaniga doimiy yashash uchun ko`chib kelganimiz sababli, meni maktabning 9-sinfiga qabul qilishingizni so`rayman; (I ask you to accept me to the 9th class of the school because I movewith my parents to Chinaz district for a permanent residence).*

Concessive subordinate clauses: *1990 yilda bizning er-xotinlik munosabatlarimiz uzilgan bo`lsa-da, nikoh rasmiy tartibda bekor qilinmagan edi. (Our marriage was abolished in 1990, although the marriage was not abolished in the formal order.)* Conditional subordinate clauses: *Agar siz ana shu kungacha mazkur so`mmani menga to`lamasangiz, men notarial idoraga murojaat etib, ijro yozuvini olishga majbur bo`lishim haqida Sizni ogohlantiraman. (I notify you that if you do not pay me that sum to this day, I will address to the notarial office that I will have to take fulfillment document.)*

Insertions may come in the content of the subordinate clauses: *Oilaviy sabablarga ko`ra (otamning og`ir kasalligi va doimiy parvarishga muhtoj bo`lib qolganligi sababli), menga 2000 yilning 10 avgustidan 16 avgustiga qadar qisqa muddatli maoshsiz ta`til berishingizni so`rayman. (For Family reasons (because of my father's illness and need for permanent care), I request that you give me a short-term vacation without paying from 10 August to 16 August in 2000.)* Here insertions show the main reason for writing a document.

Even though it is not convenient for the formal style, we can see some complicated subordinate clauses in the text of the document: *Yuqorida zikr etilgan avtomashina 80 ot kuchiga ega bo`lib, tomonlar uni 43000 (qirq uch ming) so`mga baholadik va avtomashina ana shu narxga sotildi. (The abovementioned car has 80 horsepower and we have estimated it for 43,000 (forty three thousand) sums, and the car was sold for that price.)* Here are some incongruity statements: *For Family reasons (because of my father's illness and need for permanent care), I request that you give me a short-term vacation without paying from 10 August to 16 August in 2000. Implication suggests the main reason for writing a document.*

We can see the synonymy of sentences linked without conjunction and subordinate clauses uncomplicated subordinate clauses:

The contract was made in three copies: *1-nusxa notarial idorada saqlanadi, qolgan nusxalar Q.I.Ibrohimovga avtomashinani ro`yxatdan chiqarish va ro`yxatga qo`yish uchun berildi.* (1 copy was kept in the notary's office, the remaining copies were given to K.Ibrokhimov for registration of the car.)

Shartnoma uch nusxada tuzilib, biri Yangiyo`l shahar davlat notarial idorasida saqlanadi, qolganlari avtomashinani ro`yxatdan chiqarish va ro`yxatga qo`yish uchun M.S.Mirahmedovga beriladi. (The contract is formed in three copies, one is kept in the notary's office of Yangiyul town, the rest are given to M.S. Mirakhmedov for registration of the car.)

We conclude that, the syntactic features of the style of work documents more differentiate from other styles, requirements such as formalism, honesty, accuracy, brevity, diminutiveness, semantic completeness serve to be formed peculiarity in its syntactic features.

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